

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF ZIRCONIUM. PART III. SALICYLIC AND PHENOXYACETIC ACIDS

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Two reagents, salicylic acid and phenoxyacetic acid, have been described for the separation and estimation of zirconium from many other associated elements. Titanium and quadrivalent cerium interfere. Thorium is removed in a double precipitation. Iron may be removed in a double precipitation ordinarily or in a single precipitation by complexing with excess of ammonium sulphocyanide. Other divalent and trivalent elements present no difficulty. Salicylic acid acts best in solutions of zirconium 0.18N with HCl and phenoxyacetic acid, 0.24N with HCl.

Salicylic acid was first suggested by Kolb and Ahrle (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1905, 18, 97) for the separation of thorium from cerium and lanthanum. Its ammonium salt, following Dietrich and Freund (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 86, 344), is largely employed for the removal of titanium from thorium and zirconium. The use of salicylic acid as a reagent for zirconium does not seem to have attracted attention and in this respect it possesses certain valuable properties.

Phenoxyacetic acid, a reagent first mentioned in connection with thorium by Pratt and James (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 1330), and rejected by Smith and James (*ibid.*, 1912, 34, 281), has recently been shown (Venkataramanaiah, Satyanarayanamurty and Raghava Rao, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 81) to serve a useful reagent for thorium. The reagent besides possesses useful properties for employment with zirconium.

Both reagents yield gelatinous precipitates with zirconium in slightly acid solutions and the precipitation is quantitative. As little as about 2 mg. of ZrO_2 can be conveniently estimated. Further, removal of a number of common elements as well as the rare earths of the monazite is easy.

EXPERIMENTAL

A stock solution of $ZrOCl_2$ in 0.1N-HCl was prepared as detailed in an earlier communication (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 257) and 10 ml. of this solution, when estimated with tannic acid (Scholler, *Analyst*, 1944, 69, 259), gave 0.0465 g. of ZrO_2 .

Samples of B. D. H. salicylic acid and phenoxyacetic acid laboratory reagents were purified by two crystallisations from water. The final products gave the melting points 155° and 96° respectively.

Estimation of Zirconium.—Aliquots of the stock solution of zirconyl chloride were pipetted out and to this was added 1N-HCl in sufficient quantity to give 100 ml. of a solution 0.18N in HCl in the case of salicylic acid and 0.24N in HCl in the case of phenoxyacetic acid. The solution was diluted to 100 ml. and boiled. To the boiling solution were added with stirring 100 ml. of hot 1% salicylic acid (or 2% phenoxyacetic acid) when a gelatinous precipitate formed. Boiling was continued for 10 minutes

and the beaker was set aside in a warm place, preferably over a water-bath at 70° to 80°. After settling, the precipitate was filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter, washed with a hot 0.1% solution of the reagent, dried partially and ignited to the oxide.

Table I gives the results obtained by this method.

TABLE I

ZrO ₂ taken.	ZrO ₂ obtained.		Difference.	
	A.	B.	A.	B.
0.0930 g.	0.0929 g.	0.0931 g.	-0.1 mg.	+0.1 mg.
0.0465	0.0463	0.0464	-0.2	-0.1
0.0232	0.0233	0.0232	+0.1	—
0.0116	0.0115	0.0116	-1.1	—
0.0058	0.0060	0.0057	+0.2	-0.1
0.0046	0.0044	0.0047	-0.2	+0.1
0.0023	0.0022	0.0023	-0.1	—

Effect of H⁺ ion on the Precipitation of Zirconium.—Since a few elements with which zirconium is associated are usually precipitated by these acids, their removal would have to depend on the higher solubility of the salts of the interfering elements, in other words, advantage will have to be taken of differential precipitation with varying p_H . Precipitation of zirconium under different conditions of acidity is shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Effect of p_H .

ZrO₂ taken = 0.0465 g.

Conc. of HCl in zirconyl soln.	A. Salicylic acid		Conc. of HCl in zirconyl soln.	B. Phenoxyacetic acid.	
	ZrO ₂ pptd.	Diff.		ZrO ₂ pptd.	Diff.
0.30 N	0.0400 g.	-6.5 mg.	0.30 N	0.0449 g.	-1.6 mg.
0.20	0.0455	-1.0	0.26	0.0464	-0.1
0.18	0.0464	-0.1	0.24	0.0464	-0.1
0.16	0.0466	+0.1	0.16	0.0465	—
0.12	0.0464	-0.1	0.12	0.0464	-0.1

Separation from other Elements.—The data presented in Table II indicate that a convenient acidity for the removal of other elements is 0.18 N-HCl with salicylic acid and 0.24 N-HCl with phenoxyacetic acid. Results of separations carried out under these conditions are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

ZrO₂ taken = 0.0465 g.

No.	Impurity added.	Wt. of impurity.	ZrO ₂ weighed.	
			A.	B.
1	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.1080 g.	0.0462 g.	0.0465 g.*
2	Al ₂ O ₃	0.4210	0.0463	0.0464
3	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.1088	0.0471 } 0.0464 }	0.0470 0.0465*
4	Fe ₂ O ₃ + 5 g. NH ₄ CNS		0.0462	0.0465
5	R ₂ O ₃ (cerite earths)	0.4300	0.0463	0.0463
6	MnO	0.1894	0.0363	0.0463
7	NiO	0.2055	0.0462	0.0463
8	CuO	0.1860	0.0463	0.0463
9	CaO	0.2518	0.0464	0.0463
10	BaO	0.2050	0.0462	0.0464
11	SrO	0.1799	0.0463	0.0464
12	CoO	0.1790	0.0464	0.0464
13	BeO	0.2165	0.0462	0.0466*
14	V ₂ O ₄	0.1055	0.0488	0.0486
15	ThO ₂	0.0680	0.0466*	0.0465*

A. Salicylic acid.

B. Phenoxyacetic acid.

* Double precipitation.

The carry out a double precipitation, the first precipitate after partial washing was dissolved on the filter by running through several times 35 ml. of 1:1 HCl and finally washing the filter with water. The filtrate was caught in the original beaker, the excess acid was carefully neutralised and precipitation was repeated.

The two reagents behave practically similarly. In the case of chromium alone, phenoxyacetic acid needs a second precipitation. Divalent metals present no difficulties, even so some of the trivalent metals and the cerite earths. Thorium requires a double precipitation. Quadrivalent cerium and titanium are not completely removed. The yellow titanium complex with salicylic acid is easily adsorbed on the zirconium precipitate and persists even after long washing. Digesting the precipitate with 20% ammonium salicylate improves its quality, showing highest purity. The difficulty thus appears to lie in the lower concentration of the salicylate ion obtainable in acid solution.